

First Record of *Camponotus japonicus* Mayr, 1866 (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from India

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Abstract

Camponotus japonicus Mayr, 1866 is recorded for the first time from India. Formerly, it was documented from China, Japan, Mongolia, North Korea, Pakistan, Philippines, Russia and South Korea.

Keywords: *New record, Formicinae, India.*

Received: 30 August 2021; Revised: 30 December 2021; Online: 31 December 2021

Introduction

The *Camponotus* Mayr, 1861 is a diverse genus which belongs to subfamily Formicinae. The genus has a wide distribution and occupies almost all biogeographical regions of the World (Bolton *et al.*, 2007). At present 1,053 valid species and 443 subspecies are described from all over the world (Bolton, 2021). From India the genus is represented by 75 species (Bharti *et al.*, 2016).

The significant contributions to the taxonomy of genus *Camponotus* from all over the globe include Mayr (1861), Emery (1896, 1920, 1925), Forel (1912, 1914), Arnold (1922), Wheeler (1922) and Santschi (1926, 1928). Whereas, Blaimer *et al.* (2015) and Ward *et al.* (2016) revised the classification of the genus on the basis of molecular phylogeny.

From India, taxonomic contributions include Bingham (1903), Datta & Raychaudhuri (1985), Karmaly & Narendran (2006), Bharti & Wachkoo (2014, 2015), Wachkoo (2015), Bharti *et al.* (2016), Wachkoo & Akbar (2016).

Camponotus japonicus was described by Mayr, 1866 from Japan. It has been classified as subspecies of *Camponotus pennsylvanicus* (Forel, 1879, 1904; Ruzsky, 1905) and subspecies of *Camponotus herculeanus* (Emery, 1908; Wheeler, 1906, 1909, 1921; Ruzsky, 1925; Kuznetsov-Ugamsky, 1929; Yasumatsu & Brown, 1951). Later, it was raised to species level (Bingham, 1903; Santschi, 1920, 1925;

Emery, 1925; Ruzsky, 1926; Wheeler, 1927, 1928; Karavaiev, 1929; Stitz, 1934; Yasumatsu & Brown, 1957; Arnoldi, 1967; Kupyanskaya, 1990). The species is classified as senior synonym of *Camponotus japonicus miltotus*, *Camponotus sanguinea* and *Camponotus japonicus wui* by Yasumatsu & Brown (1951). Radchenko (1997) sited it as senior synonym of *Camponotus aterrimus* (and its junior synonym *Camponotus japonicus manczshuricus*).

Mostly the colonies of *C. japonicus* are monogynous, but in some cases large colonies are found to be polygynous (Wang *et al.*, 1991). The workers prey upon small arthropods and honey dew collected from aphids (Wu & Wang, 1995). Abe (1973) mentioned that the species nests in soil in open habitats and nest entrance's open directly without a surrounding mound.

This species displays a symbiotic association with myrmecophilous *Lycaenid argyrognomon*. The caterpillars of *Lycaenid argyrognomon* pupate within the nests of *C. japonicus* in the field to protect themselves from predators (Watanabe & Hagiwara 2009 ; Mizuno *et al.*, 2018).

During the present study, we redescribed *Camponotus japonicus* Mayr, 1866 from India complemented with digital images.

Materials and Methods

Taxonomic and morphometric analysis

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was conducted using a Nikon SMZ 1500 stereo zoom microscope. Digital images of the specimens were captured using a Nikon SMZ 1500 stereomicroscope fitted with an MP (Micro Publisher) digital camera and Auto Montage (Syncroscopy, a division of synoptics Ltd.) software. All the images were cleaned with Adobe Photoshop CS5 and Helicon Filter 5. Morphological terminology and standard measurements follow Salata *et al.* (2020). Specimens examined are deposited at “Punjabi University Patiala Ant Collection” (PUAC) at Department of Zoology and Environmental Sciences, Punjabi University, Patiala, Punjab, India.

Abbreviations used

HL: head length; measured in a straight line from mid-point of anterior clypeal margin to mid-point of posterior margin of head in full-face view;

HW: head width; measured in full-face view directly above the eyes;

SL: scape length; maximum straight-line length of scape excluding the basal condylar bulb;

PW: pronotum width; maximum width of pronotum in dorsal view;

PRL: propodeum length; measured in lateral view, from metanotal suture to posterior-most point of propodeum;

PRW: propodeal width; maximum width of propodeum in dorsal view;

PTH: petiole height; the chord of ventral petiolar profile at node level is the reference line perpendicular to which the maximum height of petiole is measured in lateral view;

PTW: petiole width; maximum width of the petiolar node in lateral view;

WL: Weber's length; measured as diagonal length from the anterior end of the neck shield to the posterior margin of the propodeal lobe.

Ratios

CI: cephalic ratio, HL/HW;

SI: scape ratio, SL/HL;

PI: petiole ratio, PTH/PTW.

Result

Material examined: INDIA, Arunachal Pradesh, Tawang [27.5866°N, 91.8582°E], 1700

m, Hand picking, 08.ix.2019, 3w. Tarun Dhadwal leg. (PUAC).

Description of Worker (Figs: 1-6):

Measurements (in mm):

Major Worker: HL: 2.34-2.58, HW: 2.13-2.40, SL: 2.28-2.38, WL: 2.07-2.17, PW: 1.35-1.38, PRL: 0.63-0.65, PRW: 0.39-0.43, PTH: 0.66-1.01, PTW: 0.60-0.80, CI: 1.09-1.07, SI: 0.97-0.92, PI: 1.11-1.26 (n = 2).

Minor Worker: HL: 1.74, HW: 1.53, SL: 1.77, WL: 2.4, PW: 1.29, PRL: 0.57, PRW: 0.3, PTH: 0.72, PTW: 0.54, CI: 1.13, SI: 1.01, PI: 1.33 (n=1).

In major worker, head is longer than broad, with slightly convex lateral margins and an emarginated posterior margin. Scape long, surpasses the posterior border of head by more than a quarter of its length. Anterior margin of clypeus is convex rather than carinate. Eyes are small and prominently situated before the midlength of the head. Mandibles are short and have 6 teeth. While in the case of minor worker, head is relatively small and sub-rectangular in shape. Mandibles have 5 teeth.

Head in both major and minor worker opaque, densely microreticulate punctate. Mandibles are gleaming and punctured. Major workers have more hair on their bodies than minor workers. Short erect hair covers the posterior margin of the head. The anterior border of the clypeus is covered with long erect setae.

Mesosoma of both major and minor workers is not consistently convex, with a noticeable suture between the pronotum and the mesonotum. The mesosoma of a major worker is strong and obliquely truncate at the propodeum. In minor workers, the slope of the metanotum is less steep. Propodeal spiracle elongate. The whole surface of the mesosoma is covered in long erect and sub erect hair. Petiole node in Major worker is quite thick, anteriorly convex, and posteriorly flat. Petiole having 2 or 3 standing hair on dorsal surface.

Gaster is swathed in long golden recumbent hair. The hindtibia is prismatic, having 9 to 12 spines on the inner side of the tibia.

Body coloration: Both major and minor workers are black in colour.

Figure 1: *Camponotus japonicus* Mayr, 1866: **A:** Major worker Head, full face view; **B:** Major worker Body, lateral view; **C:** Major worker Body, dorsal view; **D:** Minor worker Head, full face view; **E:** Minor worker Body, lateral view; **F:** Minor worker Body, dorsal view.

Distribution: The species is widely distributed in China, Japan, Mongolia, North Korea, Pakistan, Philippines, Russia and South Korea.

Bionomics: The workers were collected by hand picking method over the grass near Kitpi lake from Tawang district of Arunachal Pradesh. The

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lake is situated at an elevation of 1700 meters, with an average daily temperature of 20°C.

Acknowledgments

Financial assistance rendered by the Department of Science and Technology/ Science and Engineering Research Board (SERB), (Project File No. EMR/2017/000660), Govt. of India, New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged. We also thank Forest and Wildlife Department, Government of Arunachal Pradesh, for granting the permission to collect the research material vide Order No. CWL/Gen/ 173//2018-19/pt. V11/ 2395-408 dated 05.11.2018.

References

- Abe, T. 1973. On the behavior of the ant *Camponotus japonicus* at nuptial flight. *Kontyu* 41: 333-341.
- Arnold, G. 1922. A monograph of the Formicidae of South Africa. Part V. Myrmicinae. *Annals of the South African Museum* 14: 579-674.
- Arnol'di, K.V. 1967. New data on the ant genus *Camponotus* (Hymenoptera, Formicidae) from the USSR fauna. 1. *Camponotus* (s. str.). [In Russian]. *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal* 46: 1815-1830.
- Bharti, H. and Wachkoo, A.A. 2014. A new carpenter ant, *Camponotus parabarbatus* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) from India. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 2(e996): 1-10.
- Bharti, H. and Wachkoo, A.A. 2015. Neotype designation and redescription of *Camponotus horseshoetus* (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *Acta Entomologica Musei Nationalis Pragae* 55(1): 381-385.
- Bharti, H., Guénard, B., Bharti, M. and Economo, E.P. 2016. An updated checklist of the ants of India with their specific distributions in Indian states (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). *ZooKeys* 551: 1-83.
- Bingham, C.T. 1903. The fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Hymenoptera. Ants and Cuckoo-Wasps 2. London: Taylor and Francis. 506 pp.
- Blaimer, B.B., Brady, S.G., Schultz, T.R., Lloyd, M.W., Fisher, B.L. and Ward, P.S. 2015. Phylogenomic methods outperform traditional multi-locus approaches in resolving deep evolutionary history: a case study of formicine ants. *BMC Evolutionary Biology* 15: 271.
- Bolton, B., Alpert, G., Ward, P.S. and Naskrecki, P. 2007. Bolton's Catalogue of Ants of the World: 1758-2005 [CD-ROM]. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Bolton, B. 2021. An online catalog of the ants of the world. Available from <http://antcat.org/> (Accessed 12th June, 2021)
- Datta, S.K. and Raychaudhuri, D. 1985. A new species of ant from Nagaland, North-East India. *Science and Culture* 51: 271-273
- Emery, C. 1896. Saggio di un catalogo sistematico dei generi *Camponotus*, *Polyrhachis* e affini. *Memorie della Reale Accademia delle Scienze dell'Istituto di Bologna* 5(5): 363-382 [pagination of separate: 761-780].
- Emery, C. 1908. Beiträge zur Monographie der Formiciden des paläarktischen Faunengebietes. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift* 1908: 165-205.
- Emery, C. 1920. Le genre *Camponotus* Mayr. Nouvel essai de la subdivision en sous-genres. *Revue Zoologique Africaine* (Brussels) 8: 229-260.
- Emery, C. 1925. Hymenoptera. Fam. Formicidae. Subfam. Formicinae. *Genera Insectorum* 183: 1-302.
- Forel, A. 1879. Études myrmécologiques en 1879 (deuxième partie [1re partie en 1878]). *Bulletin de la Société Vaudoise des Sciences Naturelles* 16: 53-128.
- Forel, A. 1904. Note sur les fourmis du Musée Zoologique de l'Académie Impériale des Sciences à St. Pétersbourg. *Ezhegodnik Zoologicheskago Muzeya* 8: 368-388.
- Forel, A. 1912. Formicides néotropiques. Part VI. 5me sous-famille Camponotinae Forel. *Mémoires de la Société Entomologique de Belgique* 20: 59-92.
- Forel, A. 1914. Le genre *Camponotus* Mayr et les genres voisins. *Revue Suisse de Zoologie* 22: 257-276.
- Karavaiev, V. 1929. Myrmekologische Fragmente. II. *Zbirnyk Prats' Zoolohichnoho Muzeyu*, 7, 205-220 [= Trudy. Vseukrains'ka Akademiya Nauk. Fizichno-Matematichnoho Viddilu 13:203-218].

- Karmaly, K.A. and Narendran, T.C. 2006. *Indian ants: Genus Camponotus*. Kerala: Teresian Carmel Publications. 165 pp.
- Kupyanskaya, A.N. 1990. Ants of the Far Eastern USSR. [In Russian.]. Vladivostok: Akademiya Nauk SSSR. 258pp.
- Kuznetsov-Ugamsky, N.N. 1929. Die Ameisen des Süd-Ussuri-Gebietes. Zoologischer Anzeiger 83: 16-34.
- Mayr, G. 1861. *Die europäischen Formiciden. Nach der analytischen Methode bearbeitet*. Wien: C. Gerolds Sohn, 80pp.
- Mayr, G. 1866. Diagnosen neuer und wenig gekannter Formiciden. Verhandlungen der Kaiserlich-Königlichen Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien 16: 885-908.
- Mizuno, T., Hagiwara, Y. and Akino, T. 2018. Chemical tactic of facultative myrmecophilous lycaenid pupa to suppress ant aggression. Chemoecology 28: 173-182. doi:10.1007/s00049-018-0270-8
- Radchenko, A.G. 1997. Review of ants of the genus *Camponotus* (Hymenoptera, Formicidae) of the Palearctic. The subgenus *Camponotus s. str.* [In Russian.]. Zoologicheskii Zhurnal 76: 554-564
- Ruzsky, M. 1905. The ants of Russia. (Formicariae Imperii Rossici). Systematics, geography and data on the biology of Russian ants. Part I. [In Russian.]. Trudy Obshchestva Estestvoispytatelei pri Imperatorskom Kazanskom Universitete 38 (4-6): 1-800.
- Ruzsky, M. 1925. New data on the ant fauna of Siberia. Russkoe Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie 19: 41-46
- Ruzsky, M. 1926. A systematic list of the ants found in Siberia. I. Review of the species of genera *Camponotus* (s.ext.) and *Formica* (s. str.). [In Russian.]. Izvestiya Tomskogo Gosudarstvennogo Universiteta 77: 107-111.
- Salata, S., Khalili-Moghadam, A. and Borowiec, L. 2020. Review of the *Camponotus samius* complex (Hymenoptera: Formicidae) in the Turano-Balkan region, with the description of a new species from Iran. Zootaxa 4763(4): 545-562.
- Santschi, F. 1920. Fourmis d'Indo-Chine. Annales de la Société Entomologique de Belgique 60: 158-176.
- Santschi, F. 1925. Contribution à la faune myrmécologique de la Chine. Bulletin de la Société vaudoise des sciences naturelles 56: 81-96.
- Santschi, F. 1926. Nouvelles notes sur les Camponotus. Revue Suisse de Zoologie 33: 597-618 (page 604, *Paramyrmambly* as subgenus of *Camponotus*)
- Santschi, F. 1928. Nouvelles fourmis d'Australie. Bulletin de la Société vaudoise des sciences naturelles 56: 465-483 (page 483, *Thlipsepinotus* as subgenus of *Camponotus*).
- Stitz, H. 1934. Schwedisch-chinesische wissenschaftliche Expedition nach den nordwestlichen Provinzen Chinas, unter Leitung von Dr. Sven Hedin und Prof. Sü Ping-chang. Insekten gesammelt vom schwedischen Arzt der Expedition Dr. David Hummel 1927-1930. 25. Hymenoptera. 3. Formicidae. Arkiv för Zoologi 27A (11): 1-9.
- Wachkoo, A.A. 2015. New status of the ant *Camponotus mutilarius* Emery, 1893 stat. nov. (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). Journal of Asia-Pacific Biodiversity 8(4): 382-387.
- Wachkoo, A.A. and Akbar, S.A. 2016. First description of the sexuals of *Camponotus opaciventris* Mayr, 1879 (Hymenoptera, Formicidae), with notes on distribution in Western Himalaya. Biodiversity Data Journal 4: e10464.
- Wang, C.L., Wu, J. and Xiao, G.R. 1991. A study on the bionomics and predatory effect of *Camponotus japonicus* to *Dendrolimus punctatus*. Forest Research 4: 405-408.
- Ward, P.S., Blaimer, B.B. and Fisher, B.L. 2016. A revised phylogenetic classification of the ant subfamily Formicinae (Hymenoptera: Formicidae), with resurrection of the genera *Colobopsis* and *Dinomyrmex*. Zootaxa 4072 (3): 343-357.
- Watanabe, M. and Hagiwara, Y. 2009. A newly observed form of symbiotic relationship between Reverdin's blue *Lycæides argyrognomon* and *Camponotus japonicus*. The Journal of research on the Lepidoptera 41: 70-75.

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- Wheeler, W.M. 1906. The ants of Japan. Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History 22: 301-328.
- Wheeler, W.M. 1909. Ants of Formosa and the Philippines. Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History 26: 333-345.
- Wheeler, W.M. 1921. Chinese ants. Bulletin of the Museum of Comparative Zoology 64: 529-547.
- Wheeler, W.M. 1922. *Ants of the American Museum Congo expedition*. New York: Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History. 1139pp.
- Wheeler, W.M. 1927. A few ants from China and Formosa. American Museum Novitates 259: 1-4.
- Wheeler, W.M. 1928. Ants collected by Professor F. Silvestri in Japan and Korea. Bollettino del Laboratorio di Zoologia Generale e Agraria della Reale Scuola Superiore d'Agricoltura. Portici 22: 96-125.
- Wu, J. and Wang, C.L. 1995. *The ants of China*. Beijing: China Forestry Publishing House. 214pp.
- Yasumatsu, K. and Brown, W.L., Jr. 1951. Revisional notes on *Camponotus herculeanus* Linné and close relatives in Palearctic regions (Hymenoptera: Formicidae). Journal of the Faculty of Agriculture, Kyushu University 10: 29-44.
- Yasumatsu, K. and Brown, W.L., Jr. 1957. A second look at the ants of the *Camponotus herculeanus* group in eastern Asia. Journal of the Faculty of Agriculture, Kyushu University 11: 45-51.